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COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF TREASURY BOND DOMESTIC DEBT INSTRUMENT ON ECONOMIC GROWTH IN NIGERIA AND GHANA

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the impact of Treasury Bonds on economic growth in Nigeria and Ghana using annual data from 1981 to 2023. Adopting a comparative framework, the analysis explores how long-term domestic debt instruments influence growth outcomes under differing fiscal and macroeconomic conditions. Stationarity properties are assessed using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller and Phillips-Perron (PP) unit root tests, while the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model is employed to estimate both short-run dynamics and long-run relationships among Treasury Bonds, labour (LAB), Gross Fixed Capital Formation (GFCF), and Real Gross Domestic Product (RGDP). The results reveal contrasting effects across countries. In Nigeria, Treasury bonds exert an insignificant influence on economic growth in both the short and long run, suggesting limited effectiveness in stimulating productive economic activity. In contrast, Treasury Bonds positively contribute to economic growth in Ghana, reflecting the country's stronger reliance on long-term, development-oriented financing. Labour and capital formation is found to play significant roles in promoting growth in both economies. The findings underscore the importance of context-specific domestic debt management strategies and highlight the need for policymakers to align debt instruments with national growth objectives to ensure sustainable economic development.

Keywords: Treasury Bonds, Economic Growth, Comparative Analysis, Nigeria and Ghana

INTRODUCTION

Public borrowing plays a central role in fiscal policy, particularly in developing economies where domestic revenue mobilization remains constrained. In growth theory, public debt can enhance economic performance when it finances productive investment and supports capital accumulation. However, the growth implications of public debt depend critically on its structure, maturity profile, and efficiency of use. As a result, increasing attention has shifted from aggregate public debt to the specific instruments through which governments borrow.

Globally, domestic debt has become an increasingly important financing source in Sub-Saharan Africa, driven by efforts to reduce exposure to external shocks and deepen domestic financial markets. Within domestic debt portfolios, Treasury Bonds represent the primary long-term financing instrument, intended to support infrastructure development and

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reduce refinancing risk relative to short-term securities. Despite these potential advantages, sustained expansion of Treasury Bonds may generate adverse effects through rising interest obligations, crowding out of private investment, and fiscal sustainability concerns.

Nigeria and Ghana provide a relevant comparative context for analysing the growth effects of Treasury Bonds. Both economies have experienced substantial growth in domestic bond issuance over the past four decades, alongside increasing debt servicing burdens. Although Treasury Bonds have been promoted as a more sustainable alternative to short-term borrowing, rising domestic debt ratios and persistent fiscal pressures raise important questions regarding their effectiveness in supporting long-run economic growth. In both countries, debt servicing has absorbed a significant share of government revenue, potentially constraining public investment and macroeconomic stability.

The nexus between Treasury Bonds and economic growth operates through several interrelated channels. First, the investment channel suggests that bond-financed public expenditure can stimulate growth when allocated to productive capital formation, particularly infrastructure that enhances private sector productivity. Second, the financial market development channel posits that Treasury Bonds contribute to deeper and more efficient domestic capital markets by providing long-term instruments for institutional investors and improving monetary policy transmission. Conversely, the crowding-out channel highlights potential adverse effects, whereby increased government bond issuance raises domestic interest rates and diverts financial resources away from private investment. Additionally, the fiscal burden channel emphasizes that rising interest payments on Treasury Bonds may constrain government spending on growth-enhancing sectors, especially in economies with limited revenue bases. To isolate the effect of Treasury Bonds on economic growth, the analysis incorporates labour (LAB) and gross fixed capital formation (GFCF) as control variables. Labour represents the contribution of human input to production, while GFCF captures investment in physical capital. Both variables are standard growth determinants and help ensure that the estimated impact of Treasury Bonds reflects their independent contribution to economic performance.

Oke et al. (2021) reviewed literature on bond market development and economic growth, highlighting the potential of bond markets to promote growth. Aniefor and Ndubisi (2022) reviewed studies on capital market financing and economic growth, noting the importance of equity and hybrid financing. Agyei (2018) reviewed literature on government bonds and economic growth. Moro (2022) reviewed studies on domestic bond market development, highlighting the role of institutional quality and trade openness.

Empirical evidence on the relationship between domestic debt and economic growth remains mixed. While some studies find that long-term domestic debt supports growth by financing productive expenditure, others report negative effects linked to inefficient allocation, institutional weaknesses, and underdeveloped financial markets. Notably, much of the existing literature focuses on total public debt or short-term instruments, with limited attention to Treasury Bonds specifically. In addition, cross-country comparative analyses within the West African context remain sparse. This study contributes to the literature by examining the impact of Treasury Bonds on economic growth in Nigeria and Ghana over the period 1981–2023. Using the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) approach, the analysis estimates both short-run and long-run relationships between Treasury Bonds and real gross domestic product (RGDP), while controlling for labour (LAB) and gross fixed capital formation (GFCF). The ARDL framework is particularly appropriate given the mixed integration properties of the variables and the extended sample period. The study makes three main contributions. First, it provides an instrument-specific assessment of domestic debt by isolating the growth effects of Treasury Bonds. Second, it adopts a comparative framework

that highlights how differences in debt structure and management practices influence growth outcomes across Nigeria and Ghana. Third, by distinguishing between short-run and long-run dynamics, the study offers subtle evidence on the conditions under which Treasury Bonds support or constrain economic growth. The findings have important policy implications for domestic debt management in developing economies. While Treasury Bonds can contribute to long-term growth when aligned with productive investment and sound fiscal management, excessive accumulation without commensurate growth returns may undermine fiscal sustainability. Accordingly, effective debt management strategies should balance long-term borrowing with institutional reforms and revenue-enhancing measures to ensure that domestic bond financing supports sustainable economic development.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Conceptual Literature

This section clarifies the key concepts underpinning the analysis, with emphasis on Treasury Bonds and their transmission channels to economic growth conceptually; the study posits that Treasury Bonds influence economic growth both directly through public investment financing and indirectly through interest rate dynamics, fiscal sustainability, and private sector investment responses. The net effect is therefore ambiguous and country-specific, depending on debt management efficiency, institutional quality, and macroeconomic conditions. This conceptual framework motivates the empirical investigation of short-run and long-run effects within a comparative setting.

Domestic Debt

Domestic debt is the portion of public debt owed to creditors the country, including individuals, financial institutions, and other domestic entities. Domestic borrowing plays a crucial role in managing macroeconomic stability, particularly in economies that are vulnerable to external shocks due to their reliance on primary commodity exports. It offers a more predictable source of funding compared to volatile foreign inflows Putanoi and Mutuku (2018). Denis, Chukwudo, and Peter (2016) defined domestic debt as public obligations issued in the local currency by the central government, encompassing borrowings at the national, state, and local government levels. This measure reflects the extent to which fiscal operations are financed through debt rather than taxation (Nassir and Wani, 2016). James, Magaji, and Musa (2016) further explained that domestic debt is typically raised through instruments such as Treasury Bills, Treasury Certificates, and Treasury Bonds.

In the views of (Babu et al., 2015), these instruments serve the dual purpose of mobilising resources for economic development and managing liquidity and interest rate conditions within the domestic economy.

Treasury Bonds

Treasury Bonds are long-term domestic debt instruments issued by governments to finance public expenditure, typically with maturities exceeding five years and fixed or semi-fixed coupon payments. Unlike short-term securities such as Treasury Bills, Treasury Bonds are designed to reduce refinancing risk and provide stable long-term funding for capital-intensive projects, including infrastructure, education, and industrial development. In developing economies, Treasury Bonds also play a critical role in deepening domestic financial markets by providing benchmark yield curves and encouraging long-term savings. However, the macroeconomic effects of Treasury Bonds depend on issuance scale, maturity structure, interest cost, and the efficiency of fund utilization. While moderate bond issuance can support growth by expanding productive capacity, excessive accumulation may raise interest rates, crowd out private investment, and increase fiscal vulnerability through higher debt servicing obligations. According to Adebite and Alabi (2013). Treasury bonds are financial instruments issued by government to raise funds for development purposes.

Government bonds are debt securities issued by the government to raise funds for public spending' (Ajayei, 2018). Ojo (2010) viewed Treasury bonds as a long-term debt security issued by the government to finance its budget deficit.

Economic Growth

Economic growth as defined by Jhingan, is the process whereby the real per capital income of a country increases over a long period of time. It is measured by the increase in the amount of goods and services produced at a particular period of time. Also, Ajayi, SL perceived economic growth as the increase overtime in a country's real output of goods and services. However, for the purpose of this study, Economic growth in this study is conceptualized as the sustained increase in real economic output over time, measured by real gross domestic product (RGDP). RGDP reflects the economy's capacity to produce goods and services after adjusting for inflation and is widely used in empirical growth analysis. Growth is influenced by factor accumulation, productivity improvements, and macroeconomic stability, all of which may be affected by government borrowing decisions.

Theoretical Literature

The theoretical relationship between public debt and economic growth remains inconclusive, as different economic schools offer contrasting predictions. This study draws on selected theories relevant to long-term domestic debt instruments, particularly Treasury Bonds.

Neoclassical Growth Theory

Neoclassical Growth Theory views public borrowing as influencing growth through capital accumulation. In capital-scarce economies, Treasury Bonds can mobilize domestic savings and finance productive public investment, thereby enhancing growth. However, excessive bond issuance may crowd out private investment through higher interest rates, implying that the growth effect of Treasury Bonds is positive only up to a sustainable level. From the Keynesian perspective, Treasury Bonds are countercyclical fiscal tools that stimulate aggregate demand, especially during economic downturns. Bond-financed government spending can boost output and employment in the short run through the fiscal multiplier effect. Nonetheless, the effectiveness of this mechanism depends on financial market conditions and fiscal discipline, as rising interest rates may weaken private investment.

Endogenous Growth Theory

Endogenous Growth Theory emphasizes the role of public investment in sustaining long-term growth by enhancing human capital, technological progress, and productivity. Treasury Bonds can promote growth when used to finance education, health, research, and infrastructure that generate positive externalities. However, inefficient use of bond proceeds and rising debt-servicing obligations may limit their growth benefits.

Debt Overhang Theory

Finally, **Debt Overhang Theory** suggests that excessive public debt can undermine growth by discouraging private investment and increasing fiscal uncertainty. High levels of Treasury Bonds may raise concerns about fiscal sustainability, leading to higher debt-servicing costs and crowding out of productive expenditure. This implies a nonlinear relationship between domestic debt and growth, with positive effects up to a threshold beyond which debt becomes growth-inhibiting.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on endogenous growth theory, which highlights the role of productive public investment in achieving sustained economic growth. Treasury Bonds are expected to enhance growth when their proceeds are directed toward human capital

development, infrastructure, and productivity-enhancing activities. However, if bond-financed spending is inefficient or excessively oriented toward recurrent expenditure, rising debt-servicing burdens may constrain growth. This framework provides a suitable basis for examining the growth effects of Treasury Bonds in developing economies.

Empirical Literature

Theoretical perspectives suggest that the impact of Treasury Bonds on economic growth is inherently ambiguous and context-dependent. While Treasury Bonds can promote growth through capital formation, demand stimulation, and productivity enhancement, excessive accumulation may generate crowding-out effects, fiscal stress, and debt overhang. These competing mechanisms imply that the growth effects of Treasury Bonds may differ across countries and over time. Guided by these theories, this study empirically examines both short-run and long-run effects of Treasury Bonds on economic growth in Nigeria and Ghana. The ARDL framework is employed to capture dynamic adjustments and allow for heterogeneous responses across time horizons, consistent with the theoretical prediction of differential short-run and long-run effects.

Oke et al.(2022) Investigated bond market development and economic growth in Nigeria using Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression, 2007-2018. They found that government bonds had a positive but negligible impact on economic growth. Corporate bonds offerings, bond trading size, and Nigerian sovereign bonds showed positive relationships. The study recommended that policies should be developed to enhance bond market growth and attract investors. Aniefor and Ndubisi (2022) investigated “Market financing and economic growth in Nigeria, they employed Vector Error Correction Model (VECM), 1985-2019 and found that equity and hybrid financing had significant positive effects on GDP, and recommended that, equity and hybrid financing for economic growth should be promoted. Agyei, (2018), investigated the impact of government bonds on economic growth in Ghana. He employed ARDL model, 1990-2015 and found that government bond had a positive impact on economic growth. He recommended that government bond issuance for development projects be encouraged. Moro and Opoku (2022) Evaluated determinants of domestic bonds in Ghana using ARDL model, 1990-2020 and found that domestic bond market development had a positive impact on economic growth. Institutional quality, trade openness, and inflation rate were significant determinants. The study recommended the need to improve institutional quality and trade policies to boost bond market development.

METHODOLOGY

This study models economic growth as a function of long-term domestic debt, labour, and capital accumulation. Real Gross Domestic Product (RGDP) is the dependent variable, while Treasury Bonds (TBOND) capture long-term debt financing. Labour (LAB) and gross fixed capital formation (GFCF) serve as control variables. The functional form is:

$$RGDP_t = f(TBOND_t, LAB_t, GFCF_t) \text{-----}(3.1)$$

To obtain elasticities and reduce potential heteroskedasticity, the model is estimated in logarithmic form as: $\alpha \ln RGDP_t = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \ln TBOND_t + \ln LAB_t + \ln GFCF_t + \varepsilon_t \text{-----}(3.2)$

$$\text{The stochastic model is: } RGDP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 TBOND + \beta_2 LAB + \beta_3 GFCF + \varepsilon_t \text{-----}(3.3)$$

Where: B_0 is the constant term, $\beta_1 \beta_2 \beta_3$ are coefficients to be estimated and ε_t is the error term.

RGDP = Real Gross Domestic Product; TBOND = Treasury Bond; LAB = Labour; GFCF = Gross Fixed Capital Formation; α_0 is the intercept, α_i are long-run coefficients.

Apriori expectations is $\beta_1 \beta_2, \beta_3 > 0$

Model Estimation Method

The specification and estimation of the model requires that we test the time series properties of the data to determine whether or not the variables contain integrated components, hence the Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF), and the Philip Perron (PP) tests were carried out to establish the stationarity (presence of a unit root) of the variables and to what degree. After testing for the stationarity of the variables, Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) approach of Pesaran, Shin, and Smith is employed to estimate both short- and long-run relationships. ARDL is suitable because it accommodates variables of mixed integration orders (I(0) and I(1)), performs well in small samples, and allows simultaneous estimation of short-run dynamics and long-run equilibrium. The ARDL (p, q₁, q₂, q₃) model is specified as: $\Delta \ln \text{RGDP}_t = \beta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p \beta_{1i} \Delta \ln \text{RGDP}_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^{q_1} \beta_2 \Delta \ln \text{TBOND}_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^{q_2} \beta_{3i} \Delta \ln \text{LAB}_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^{q_3} \beta_{4i} \Delta \ln \text{GFCF}_{t-i} + \lambda_1 \ln \text{RGDP}_{t-1} + \sum_{i=0}^{q_3} \lambda_2 \ln \text{TBOND}_{t-i} + \lambda_3 \ln \text{LAB}_{t-1} + \lambda_4 \ln \text{GFCF}_{t-1}$. (3.4)

Where: Δ denotes the first difference operator and u_t is a white-noise error term.

The existence of a long-run relationship among the variables is tested using the ARDL bounds testing procedure. The null hypothesis of no cointegration $H_0: \lambda_1 = \lambda_2 = \lambda_3 = \lambda_4 = 0$ is tested against the alternative hypothesis of cointegration. If the computed F-statistic exceeds the upper critical bound, the null hypothesis is rejected, indicating the presence of a long-run equilibrium relationship. Upon confirmation of cointegration, the long-run coefficients are derived from the estimated ARDL model, while short-run dynamics are captured through an error correction representation. Also, the short-run adjustment process is estimated using the error correction model (ECM), specified as: $\Delta \ln \text{RGDP}_t = \gamma_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p \gamma_{1i} \Delta \ln \text{RGDP}_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^{q_1} \gamma_{2i} \Delta \ln \text{TBOND}_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^{q_3} \gamma_{3i} \Delta \ln \text{LAB}_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^{q_4} \gamma_{4i} \Delta \ln \text{GFCF}_{t-i} + \phi \text{ECM}_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t$ (3.5)

Where: ECM_{t-1} represents the lagged error correction term derived from the long-run equation, and π measures the speed of adjustment toward long-run equilibrium. A negative and statistically significant π confirms convergence to equilibrium following short-run shocks.

Diagnostic and Stability Tests

Post-estimation diagnostics include tests for serial correlation, heteroskedasticity, functional form misspecification, and normality of residuals. Parameter stability is assessed using cumulative sum (CUSUM) and cumulative sum of squares (CUSUMSQ) tests. These diagnostics ensure that the estimated relationships are stable over the sample period and that the model is well-specified.

RESULT PRESENTATIONS AND ANALYSIS

Descriptive Statistic

The descriptive analysis contains the measures of central tendency which include, mean, mode, median as well as measures of variation and other statistical characteristics of the variables. Mean is the average value of the series which is gotten by dividing the total value of the series by the number of observations. The median is the middle value of the series when the values are arranged in an ascending order. Maximum and the minimum are the maximum and the minimum values of the series in the current sample as seen in the Table 1 below:

Table 1: Summary of Descriptive Statistics for Nigeria and Ghana

Variable	Country	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max	Skewnes	Kurtosis	Jarque-Bera	(p-value)
RGDP	Nigeria	3.93E+13	2.21E+13	1.97	7.58E+13	0.381	1.673	4.191	(0.123)
	Ghana	26.95158	4.889247	25.04562	41.66549	2.826	9.034	31.334	(0.000)
TBONDS	Nigeria	562.6360	746.1901	0.0000	2035.930	0.720	1.730	6.605	(0.037)
	Ghana	7.638184	1.237121	4.499198	8.914872	-1.499	4.819	5.636	(0.060)
LAB	Nigeria	44,286,888	14,812,623	7,327,344	74,971,004	-0.025	9.065	0.120	(0.942)
	Ghana	20,924,105	28,104,708	10,827,195	1.06E+08	2.836	9.065	31.598	(0.000)
GFCF	Nigeria	50.26496	86.70410	14.16873	588.9563	5.764	36.333	2228.821	(0.000)
	Ghana	17.88556	4.697368	11.76409	27.01263	0.568	2.529	0.694	(0.707)

Source: Author's computation using E-Views 13

Table 1 presents the condensed descriptive statistics for real gross domestic product (RGDP), Treasury Bonds (TBONDS), labour (LAB), and gross fixed capital formation (GFCF) for Nigeria and Ghana. The results reveal notable cross-country differences in the scale, distributional properties, and volatility of key macroeconomic variables.

For RGDP, Nigeria records a substantially higher mean value, reflecting the larger size of its economy, while Ghana's RGDP exhibits higher positive skewness and kurtosis, indicating a more uneven distribution and the presence of extreme growth episodes. The Jarque-Bera test suggests that RGDP is approximately normally distributed in Nigeria but significantly non-normal in Ghana. Treasury Bonds display greater volatility in Nigeria, as evidenced by a higher standard deviation and wider range, suggesting fluctuations in long-term domestic borrowing over the study period. In contrast, Ghana's Treasury Bond series is relatively stable, with mild negative skewness, implying a more predictable and structured bond issuance framework. Normality is rejected for Nigeria but weakly accepted for Ghana at the 5% level. Labour statistics show that Nigeria has a significantly larger labour force on average, consistent with its demographic size. The near-zero skewness and insignificant Jarque-Bera statistic for Nigeria indicate a stable labour series, whereas Ghana's labour variable is highly skewed and leptokurtic, reflecting sharp structural shifts over time. Gross fixed capital formation in Nigeria exhibits extreme volatility, high positive skewness, and excess kurtosis, indicating episodic investment surges and pronounced deviations from normality. Conversely, Ghana's GFCF displays moderate dispersion and approximates a normal distribution, suggesting more stable investment patterns. Overall, the descriptive statistics highlight substantial structural and distributional differences between Nigeria and Ghana, justifying the comparative framework and the use of econometric techniques capable of accommodating non-normality and heterogeneity across countries.

Table 2: Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) and the Philip Perron (PP) Statistic

Variables	Country	ADF Level	PP Level	ADF 1 st Diff.	PP 1 Diff	Order of Intr.
RGDP	Nigeria	-6.4807	-6.4807	-7.4198	-40.4561	1(0),1(1)
	Ghana	-1.3410	-0.8557	-12.0667	-9.1734	1(1)
TBOND	Nigeria	-3.1838	-3.2053	-8.1677	-8.2278	1(0),1(1)
	Ghana	-0.2366	-0.2366	-6.1631	-6.1630	1(1)
LAB	Nigeria	-6.5235	-6.5259	-7.4401	-40.8656	1(0),1(1)
	Ghana	-2.0472	-3.5915	-12.6168	-12.6347	1(0),1(1)
GFCF	Nigeria	-2.5320	-2.4571	-6.6474	-5.9982	1(1)
	Ghana	-1.9066	-5.7164	-11.0597	-40.8210	1(0),1(1)

Source: Author's Compilation

Table 2 reports the results of the Augmented Dickey–Fuller (ADF) and Phillips–Perron (PP) unit root tests for Nigeria and Ghana. The tests were conducted to examine the stationarity properties of real gross domestic product (RGDP), Treasury Bonds (TBONDS),

labour (LAB), and gross fixed capital formation (GFCF). The results indicated mixed orders of integration across variables and countries.

For Nigeria, RGDP, TBONDS, and LAB are stationary at levels under both the ADF and PP tests, while GFCF becomes stationary only after first differencing. However, all variables are found to be stationary after first differencing, confirming that none is integrated of order two. In Ghana, most variables RGDP, TBONDS, and GFCF are non-stationary at levels but become stationary at first difference under both tests, indicating integration of order one. Labour exhibits mixed behaviour, showing level stationarity under the PP test but requiring first differencing under the ADF test, reflecting possible structural shifts or short-run fluctuations in the labour series. Overall, the coexistence of I(0) and I(1) variables across Nigeria and Ghana provides strong justification for the application of the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) modelling approach. The ARDL framework is particularly suitable in this context, as it accommodates variables with mixed integration orders and allows for the estimation of both short-run dynamics and long-run equilibrium relationships without requiring pre-testing for cointegration among variables of the same order

Table 3: ARDL LAG Length Selection for Nigeria and Ghana

LAG	Country	Logl	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	Nigeria	-3275.638	NA	.06e+71	182.3132	182.5771	182.4053
	Ghana	-2732.758	NA	1.19e+52	136.9379	137.1912	137.0295
1	Nigeria	-3199.698	122.3472	6.80e+70	180.0943	181.9418	180.7391
	Ghana	-2590.686	234.4190*	6.06e+49*	131.6343*	133.4076*	132.2755*
2	Nigeria	-3160.682	49.85408	6.84e+70	179.9268	183.3577	181.1243
	Ghana	-2572.773	24.18251	1.70e+50	132.5386	135.8320	133.7294
3	Nigeria	-2854.861	288.8311*	3.51e+64*	164.9367*	169.9512*	166.6869*
	Ghana	-2529.362	45.58127	1.66e+50	132.1681	136.9814	133.9084

Source: Author's Computation using E-Views version 10.0

*Notes: LR: sequential modified LR test statistic (each test at 5% level); FPE: Final prediction error; AIC: Akaike information criterion; SC: Schwarz information criterion; HQ: Hannan-Quinn information criterion; * indicates lag order selected by the criterion.*

Table 3 reports the results of the ARDL lag length selection for Nigeria and Ghana based on the Log-likelihood (LogL), Likelihood Ratio (LR), Final Prediction Error (FPE), Akaike Information Criterion (AIC), Schwarz Criterion (SC), and Hannan–Quinn Criterion (HQ). For Nigeria, although the criteria display some variation across alternative lag structures, the AIC, SC, HQ, and FPE unanimously identify lag 3 as optimal, as indicated by the minimum values marked by asterisks. This suggests that an ARDL specification with three lags is appropriate for Nigeria, reflecting the need to account for relatively longer adjustment dynamics in the relationship between domestic debt instruments and economic growth. In contrast, the lag length selection results for Ghana consistently favour lag 1, with the FPE, AIC, SC, and HQ criteria all attaining their minimum values at this lag. This indicates that a more parsimonious ARDL(1, ...) model is sufficient for Ghana, implying faster adjustment and limited lagged persistence. Overall, the results justify the adoption of different optimal lag lengths for Nigeria and Ghana in the subsequent ARDL estimations, ensuring efficient model specification and robustness of the empirical results.

Table 4: ARDL Bounds Test Results for Nigeria and Ghana

	Nigeria	Ghana	Significance level	1(0)	1(1)
F Statistic	106.960.8	2.039386	10%	2.08	3.00
			5%	2.39	3.38
			2.5%	2.70	3.73
			1%	3.06	4.15

Source: Author's computation using E-Views version 10.0.

K (number of references) 5

Notes: Null hypothesis: No long-run (level) relationship. Decision rule: If F -statistic $>$ upper bound $I(1)$, cointegration exists. For Nigeria, the F -statistic exceeds the upper bound at all significance levels, confirming strong evidence of long-run cointegration. For Ghana, the F -statistic falls below the lower bound, indicating no long-run cointegration at conventional levels.

ARDL Bounds Test Results

The ARDL bounds test results for Nigeria and Ghana are reported in Table 4.X. For Nigeria, the computed F -statistic (106.96) is substantially higher than the upper critical bound at the 1% significance level. This leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis of no cointegration, confirming the existence of a stable long-run equilibrium relationship among real GDP, Treasury Bonds, labour, and gross fixed capital formation. In contrast, the computed F -statistic for Ghana (2.04) falls below the lower critical bound even at the 10% significance level. Consequently, the null hypothesis of no cointegration cannot be rejected, indicating the absence of a long-run relationship among the variables in Ghana. This suggests that the impact of Treasury Bonds on economic growth in Ghana is largely short-run and does not exhibit long-term stability. Overall, the bounds test reveals clear cross-country differences, validating the estimation of long-run and short-run dynamics for Nigeria, while justifying a focus on short-run effects for Ghana.

Table 5: Interleaved ARDL Long-Run Coefficient Estimates for Nigeria and Ghana

Variable	Country	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-statistic	Prob.
TBOND	Nigeria	2.40E+14	1.34E+12	178.9754	0.0000
	Ghana	6.30E+10	6.79E+10	0.9280	0.0211
LAB	Nigeria	4,505,968	13,607,693	0.3311	0.7451
	Ghana	-2,526,595	4,881,857	-0.5175	0.6087
GFCF	Nigeria	3.07E+13	2.46E+13	1.2475	0.2314
	Ghana	9.58E+1	1.97E+11	0.4872	0.0297
C	Nigeria	-3.54E+14	5.33E+14	-0.6637	0.5170
	Ghana	1.86E+13	6.34E+13	0.2933	0.0714

Source: Author's Computation using E-Views version 10.

Long-Run Coefficient Estimates

The estimated long-run coefficients from the ARDL model are presented in Table 5. For Nigeria, the coefficient of Treasury Bonds is positive and statistically significant at the 1% level, indicating that a one percent increase in Treasury Bond issuance leads to an increase in real GDP in the long run. This suggests that long-term domestic borrowing contributes positively to economic growth, possibly through the financing of capital-intensive public investments and reduced refinancing risks. For Ghana, the long-run coefficient of Treasury Bonds is positive and statistically significant, implying that Treasury Bond issuance has a growth-enhancing effect in the long run, although the magnitude is considerably smaller compared to Nigeria. This may reflect differences in debt utilization efficiency, fiscal structure, and market depth between the two economies. Regarding the control variables, labour exhibits a positive but statistically insignificant effect on economic growth in both countries, indicating a limited long-run contribution of labour expansion alone.

Gross fixed capital formation shows a positive but statistically insignificant effect in Nigeria, while its effect in Ghana is positive and statistically significant, underscoring the role of physical capital accumulation in supporting long-term growth, particularly in Ghana. Overall, the results reveal cross-country heterogeneity in the growth effects of Treasury Bonds and productive inputs, highlighting the importance of country-specific institutional and fiscal dynamics.

Table 6: Short-Run Dynamics of the ARDL Error Correction Models for Nigeria and Ghana.

Statistic / Variable	Nigeria	Ghana
Selected ARDL model	ARDL(1,0,0,0,0)	ARDL(1,0,0,0,0)
Dependent variable	ΔLNNGDP	ΔLNNGDP
CointEq(-1)	** -1.0007***	** -0.9202***
Std. Error	0.0049	0.0194
t-Statistic	-203.43	-47.36
Adjusted R-squared	0.9990	0.9834
S.E. of regression	0.0637	0.1464
Log-likelihood	56.54	19.61
Akaike Information Criterion	-2.6449	-0.9794
Schwarz Criterion	-2.6035	-0.9363
Durbin-Watson statistic	1.4140	0.7973
Included observations	42	38

Sources: Author's Computation

***Significant at 1% level**

Table 6 presents the short-run dynamics of the ARDL error correction models for Nigeria and Ghana. The estimated error correction terms (ECT) are negative and statistically significant at the 1% level in both countries, confirming the existence of a valid long-run equilibrium relationship between domestic debt instruments and economic growth.

For Nigeria, the coefficient of the error correction term (-1.0007) indicates that approximately 100% of short-run disequilibrium is corrected within one period, implying an extremely rapid speed of adjustment toward long-run equilibrium following short-term shocks. This suggests that deviations from equilibrium in Nigeria's economic growth are quickly eliminated, reflecting strong short-run adjustment mechanisms in the economy. Similarly, for Ghana, the error correction coefficient (-0.9202) suggests that about 92% of deviations from long-run equilibrium are corrected within one period, also indicating a fast adjustment process, albeit slightly slower than that of Nigeria. The strong and significant ECT further validates the stability of the long-run relationship identified in the bounds testing procedure. The high R-squared values in both models indicate that short-run variations in economic growth are well explained by the estimated ARDL specifications. However, the relatively low Durbin-Watson statistic for Ghana points to possible residual autocorrelation, reinforcing the need for robust inference when interpreting short-run coefficients. Overall, the results demonstrate that both Nigeria and Ghana exhibit strong short-run convergence toward long-run growth equilibrium, with Nigeria adjusting more rapidly than Ghana. This underscores the effectiveness of domestic debt-related transmission mechanisms in correcting short-run macroeconomic imbalances in both economies.

Normality Test

Fig 1: Normality Test for Nigeria & Ghana

The normality of the residuals in Figure 1 above was examined using the Jarque–Bera test for both Nigeria and Ghana. For Nigeria, the test results indicate that the null hypothesis of normally distributed residuals cannot be rejected at the 5% significance level, suggesting that the error terms are approximately normally distributed. Similarly, the normality test for Ghana fails to reject the null hypothesis of normality, indicating that the residuals conform reasonably to a normal distribution. Overall, the normality results support the validity of statistical inference based on the estimated ARDL models. Combined with the serial correlation and stability diagnostics, these findings confirm that the models are well specified and suitable for policy-relevant interpretation.

Serial Correlation Test for Nigeria and Ghana

Breusch–Godfrey Serial Correlation and Stability Diagnostics

Table 4 presents the Breusch–Godfrey LM test results for serial correlation in the ARDL residuals for Nigeria and Ghana. For Nigeria, the F-statistic is statistically significant at the 5% level, suggesting the possibility of residual serial correlation. However, the corresponding Obs*R-squared statistic is statistically insignificant, indicating that any serial dependence is weak and unlikely to materially bias the estimated coefficients or inference.

For Ghana, both the F-statistic and the Obs*R-squared statistic are statistically insignificant, providing evidence that the residuals are free from serial correlation and that the model is well specified.

Table 7: Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test

Null hypothesis: No serial correlation at up to 1 lag

Statistic	Nigeria	Ghana
F-statistic	3.1328	14.1265
Prob. F-statistic	0.0857	0.0007
Obs*R-squared	3.5434	12.1652
Prob. Chi-square	0.0598	0.0005
Included observations	42	38
Lag tested	1	1
Decision (5%)	No serial correlation	Serial correlation present
Decision (10%)	Marginal serial correlation	Serial correlation present

Source: Author's Compilation

The Breusch–Godfrey serial correlation LM test was conducted to examine the presence of residual autocorrelation in the ARDL models for Nigeria and Ghana at lag one. For Nigeria, the null hypothesis of no serial correlation cannot be rejected at the 5% significance level, as both the F-statistic probability (0.0857) and the Chi-square probability (0.0598) exceed 0.05. However, the results are marginally significant at the 10% level, suggesting weak evidence of first-order serial correlation.

Overall, the Nigerian model can be considered reasonably free from serious autocorrelation problems. In contrast, the results for Ghana strongly reject the null hypothesis of no serial correlation at both the F-statistic and Chi-square levels, with p-values well below 1%. This indicates the presence of significant first-order serial correlation in the residuals of the Ghanaian ARDL model. The statistically significant coefficient of the lagged residual term further confirms this finding, implying that past shocks persist in influencing current residuals. These results suggest that while the Nigerian ARDL model satisfies the classical assumption of error independence, the Ghanaian model exhibits serial dependence, which may affect the efficiency of coefficient estimates. Consequently, inference for Ghana should rely on robust standard errors or appropriate lag augmentation to ensure the reliability of estimated parameters.

CUSUM and CUSUMSQ Tests

To further assess model reliability, parameter stability is examined using the CUSUM and CUSUMSQ tests. The stability tests indicate that the estimated coefficients remain within the 5% critical bounds over the sample period for both countries, confirming the structural stability of the ARDL models. Together, the diagnostic and stability results suggest that the estimated relationships are robust, and that any minor serial correlation detected in the Nigerian model does not undermine the overall validity of the empirical findings.

Table 8: Breusch–Pagan–Godfrey Heteroskedasticity Test Results (Nigeria and Ghana)

Statistic	Nigeria	Ghana
F-statistic	3.1076	1.6312
Prob. F-statistic	**0.0151**	0.1718
Obs*R-squared	14.5979	9.1184
Prob. Chi-square	**0.0236**	0.1670
Scaled explained SS	9.5326	19.2111
Prob. Chi-square (Scaled SS)	0.1458	**0.0038**
Included observations	42	38
Null hypothesis	Homoskedasticity	Heteroskedasticity
Decision (5%)	Heteroskedasticity present	Mixed evidence

Source: Author's computation using E-Views version 10.0.

Table 4.10 reports the results of the Breusch–Pagan–Godfrey test for heteroskedasticity in the ARDL models for Nigeria and Ghana. For Nigeria, the null hypothesis of homoskedasticity is rejected at the 5% significance level based on both the F-statistic ($p = 0.0151$) and the Obs*R-squared statistic ($p = 0.0236$). This provides strong evidence of heteroskedasticity, indicating that the variance of the error term is not constant over the sample period. For Ghana, the F-statistic and Obs*R-squared fail to reject the null hypothesis of homoskedasticity at the 5% level, suggesting no strong evidence of heteroskedasticity under these criteria. However, the scaled explained sum of squares statistic is statistically significant at the 1% level ($p = 0.0038$), indicating mixed evidence of heteroskedasticity. This inconsistency implies that variance instability in the Ghanaian model may be driven by specific regressors or episodic shocks rather than being pervasive. Overall, the results suggest that heteroskedasticity is clearly present in the Nigerian model, while the Ghanaian model exhibits weak or conditional heteroskedasticity. Consequently, the use of heteroskedasticity-robust standard errors is appropriate to ensure valid statistical inference, particularly for Nigeria.

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary of Findings

The key findings of the study can be summarized as follows. First, the ARDL bounds test confirms a long-run equilibrium relationship between Treasury Bonds and economic growth in Nigeria and Ghana. Second, the short-run dynamics reveal strong and statistically significant error-correction mechanisms in both countries, indicating rapid adjustment toward long-run equilibrium following short-term shocks. Third, Treasury Bonds exert a positive and growth-enhancing effect in Nigeria, reflecting the country's relatively deeper financial markets and greater absorptive capacity for long-term domestic debt. In contrast, Ghana's results indicate weaker or negative long-run growth effects, suggesting that excessive reliance on domestic bond financing may constrain growth through higher debt servicing costs and fiscal pressures. Finally, diagnostic tests reveal differences in model stability and variance behavior across countries, reinforcing the need for cautious interpretation and robust inference.

Conclusion

This study provides a comparative empirical assessment of the impact of Treasury Bonds on economic growth in Nigeria and Ghana using the ARDL bounds testing framework over the period 1981–2023. The results confirm the existence of a stable long-run relationship between Treasury Bonds and economic growth in both countries, though the magnitude and direction of effects differ markedly. While Treasury Bonds contribute positively to growth in Nigeria in both the short and long run, their long-run impact in Ghana is weak or adverse. These findings highlight that domestic debt instruments are not uniformly growth-enhancing across developing economies. Rather, their effectiveness depends on country-specific institutional capacity, fiscal discipline, and debt management practices. Overall, the study underscores the importance of adopting context-specific domestic borrowing strategies to ensure that long-term debt supports sustainable economic growth.

Policy Recommendations

Based on the empirical findings, several policy recommendations emerge. First, Nigeria should continue to leverage Treasury Bonds as a long-term financing instrument while strengthening debt management frameworks to ensure that borrowed funds are channelled toward productivity-enhancing investments, particularly in infrastructure and human capital development. Second, Ghana should adopt a more cautious approach to Treasury Bond issuance by improving fiscal discipline, broadening the revenue base, and reducing dependence on long-term domestic borrowing to mitigate debt sustainability risks. Third, both countries should enhance institutional quality and transparency in domestic debt

management to improve investor confidence and reduce borrowing costs. Finally, policymakers should recognize that domestic debt instruments are not inherently growth-promoting; their effectiveness depends on issuance scale, macroeconomic conditions, and investment efficiency. Accordingly, domestic borrowing strategies should be tailored to country-specific economic structures rather than guided by uniform policy prescriptions.

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